

TEACHER-LEARNER RAPPORT AND READING ENGAGEMENT ON ELEMENTARY LEARNERS IN MACO NORTH DISTRICT

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Abstract. The study unfolded the of challenges of teacher-learner rapport and on reading engagement among Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that extent of challenges of teacher-learner rapport in terms of special needs students, teacher burn-out, transitions and mobility and diverse learning styes are oftentimes manifested; while, technology distractions is sometimes manifested, thus extensive, and, likewise, extent of reading engagement in terms of interactions in reading material, use of reading strategy and sustained focus are oftentimes manifested; independent reading choices is sometimes manifested, is extensive. There is a significant relationship between teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement. All domains of challenges of teacher-learner rapport in terms of diverse learning styles, technology destructions, special needs students, transitions and mobility, and teacher burnout significantly influenced reading engagement. Future research may explore effective interventions and strategies to overcome these challenges, considering cultural, socio-economic, and educational context variables.

KEY WORDS

1. Challenges of teacher-learner rapport.
2. reading engagement.
3. technology distractions.

1. Introduction

Teacher-learner rapport in an international setting encompasses the unique dynamics of multicultural and diverse classrooms, where educators and students from various cultural backgrounds come together to learn and interact. In this globalized educational landscape, fostering positive rapport becomes a paramount goal, as it influences academic success and plays a pivotal role in creating a culturally inclusive and enriching learning environment. In international

settings, teachers are tasked with bridging cultural gaps, understanding diverse learning needs, and embracing various perspectives.

Building rapport becomes a delicate interplay of effective communication, empathy, and cultural sensitivity. It involves acknowledging and valuing students' diverse experiences and identities, establishing trust, respect, and inclusivity. Successful teacher-learner rapport in international contexts enhances academic achieve-

ment, promotes intercultural understanding, and prepares students to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world. It's a testament to the power of education to transcend borders and foster meaningful connections among individuals from diverse backgrounds (Irwin, 2022). Teacher-learner rapport in the Philippine setting is characterized by a strong emphasis on respect, warmth, and a sense of shared community within the classroom. Filipino culture places a high value on interpersonal relationships, which is reflected in the educational context. In Philippine classrooms, teachers often act as mentors and role models, and students typically show deep respect for their educators. Building rapport goes beyond the academic sphere; it involves creating a supportive and nurturing environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and asking questions. This approach allows for open communication and encourages active student participation. Additionally, the strong camaraderie and mutual support within the Philippine classroom fosters a positive and engaging learning experience. Teacher-learner rapport is vital for academic success and plays a significant role in shaping students' values, character, and sense of belonging within their educational community (Delos Reyes and Torio, 2021). The challenges of teacher-learner rapport in the Philippine setting are multi-faceted, reflecting the complexities of the educational landscape in the country. One significant challenge stems from the large class sizes, making it difficult for teachers to provide individualized attention and build strong connections with each student. Moreover, students' diverse socio-economic backgrounds and cultural diversity present additional hurdles. Teachers must navigate these differences to create an inclusive and equitable learning environment (Phillips, 2023). Another challenge is the pressure of standardized testing and curriculum demands, which can limit the time available for fostering rapport. Additionally, the use of technology and social media, while providing new opportunities for communication, can also pose distractions and barriers to building meaningful face-to-face relationships. Despite these challenges, Philippine educators are known for their resilience and dedication. They often find innovative ways to overcome obstacles and create supportive, rapport-rich classrooms where students can thrive academically and personally (Bonner et.al., 2023). The extent of reading engagement among Grade 1 learners in the Philippine setting can be significantly influenced by the challenges related to teacher-learner rapport. These challenges, such as large class sizes, diverse student backgrounds, and curriculum demands, can impact the individualized attention and support teachers can provide each student. In turn, this may affect students' levels of engagement with reading materials. When these challenges hinder teacher-learner rapport, students may find it more challenging to develop a strong sense of trust and connection with their educators, which can motivate them to engage with reading materials enthusiastically. However, it's important to note that Filipino teachers often exhibit remarkable dedication and resourcefulness in fostering positive learning environments. By implementing innovative strategies and personalized approaches, educators in the Philippines continue to work towards enhancing the reading engagement of Grade 1 learners, regardless of the challenges they may face in building rapport (Delos Reyes, 2021). In Maco North, Davao de Oro Province, several possible interventions exist to overcome challenges and increase learner engagement in reading. First, addressing the challenge of limited resources, the community and local authorities can work together to establish well-equipped school libraries and reading corners with a diverse collection of age-appropriate and culturally relevant books. Providing teachers with professional development in literacy instruction and classroom management tailored to the

specific needs of the learners is essential. Furthermore, parent and community involvement can be encouraged through literacy programs and workshops, fostering a culture of reading at home. To address potential teacher-learner rapport issues, creating smaller class sizes or implementing peer mentoring programs can provide students with more personalized attention and emotional support. Leveraging technology and e-learning platforms can also make reading materials more accessible, engaging, and interactive for learners. Additionally, community outreach efforts, such as literacy campaigns, book drives, and storytelling sessions, can promote reading as a shared experience. Thus, this study is conducted.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps for conducting the study. These include selecting the study's design, the respondents and sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are essential to ensuring appropriateness and correctness and to producing sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The researcher used artificial intelligence methods for proofreading when preparing this publication. In particular, AI was used to improve the manuscript's overall quality, coherence, and correctness. The purpose of clearly stating this approach is to uphold research ethics and transparency. The use of AI for proofreading recognizes the growing presence and potential of AI in academic and professional writing and demonstrates a commitment to utilizing cutting-edge technologies responsibly.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. This design is a comprehensive approach to research methodology that combines several key elements to explore relationships and systematically predict outcomes. It typically involves observing and analyzing existing data or naturally occurring phenomena without intervention, manipulation, or control of variables (Creswell, 2014). Descriptive aspects involve providing a detailed account or depiction of a particular situation, event, or group, often through surveys, observations, or content analysis. Correlational research seeks to identify and quantify relationships or associations between variables, allowing researchers to determine if changes in one variable correspond to changes in another. On the other hand, predictive research utilizes statistical techniques to forecast future outcomes based on patterns and relationships identified in the data. Moreover, a descriptive-correlational research design can help generate hypotheses and identify potential causal relationships between variables. By examining the strength and direction of correlations between variables, researchers can gain insight into how changes in one variable might be associated with changes in another. This can provide a basis for developing theories about the underlying mechanisms that drive the relationship between variables, which can be tested using more rigorous experimental or quasi-experimental designs. Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design can be valuable when experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, manipulating variables such as age, gender, or medical condition to examine their effects on other variables may be unethical. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest without requiring manipulation or control of those variables. By adopting a non-

experimental descriptive design, researchers can gather rich, real-world data that accurately portrays teacher-learner rapport and its associated challenges. This design allows exploring multiple variables related to rapport and reading engagement without intervening in the natural classroom setting. Additionally, the correlational aspect of the research design enables researchers to identify potential relationships and associations between specific challenges in teacher-learner rapport and levels of reading engagement among students. Furthermore, the predictive component of the study facilitates the development of models or hypotheses that can help educators and policymakers anticipate how changes or interventions in rapport-building strategies may impact future reading engagement outcomes. Overall, this research design provides valuable insights into the multifaceted relationship between teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement, offering data-driven recommendations for enhancing the educational experience for students.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary Teachers in Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. She used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective School within the Maco North District. One randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face-to-face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents are selected because they are assumed to have been engaged in teaching reading, especially to elementary learners. They are qualified for the role and are expected to have performed and contributed to improving the schools and the learners' awareness and ed-

ucational stages given the new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly implemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher gathered and read reviews of related literature to develop concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literature as argued by the authors. Two parts of the survey questionnaire consisted of indicators of challenges of teacher-learner rapport in terms of diverse learning styles, technology distractions, special needs students, transitions and mobility, and teacher burnout. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured reading engagement regarding interest in reading material, use of reading strategies, sustained focus, and independent reading choices. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.884, which means that the unidimensional reliability when it comes to internal consistency is very good.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the challenges of teacher-learner report. Scale, descriptive rating and interpretation are provided below:

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Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teacher-learner rapport is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teacher-learner rapport is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teacher-learner rapport is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teacher-learner rapport is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teacher-learner rapport is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of reading engagement, a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The reading engagement is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The reading engagement is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The reading engagement is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The reading engagement is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The reading engagement is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct the study. The second week of October 2023, the researcher started conceptualizing the thesis proposal’s contents and objective. She then prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004). From the last week of January up to the first week of February 2024, as soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the Elementary schools of Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In March 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process,

which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents without internet access. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of May 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of April 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime in the last week of March 2024 and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the second week of June 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1), the extent of challenges of teacher-learner rapport, and statement problem number two (2), the extent of reading engagement in Maco North District, Davao de Oro Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship between challenges of

teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of challenges of teacher-learner rapport that significantly influence reading engagement (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations follow when results are available.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the researcher addresses the collection of data and its subsequent presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Both tabular and textual formats are employed to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Additionally, these presentations serve as supporting evidence for the hypothesis put forth.

Table 1 summarizes the extent of teacher-learner rapport challenges. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: special needs students (3.89), teacher burnout (3.68), transitions and mobility (3.46), and diverse learning styles (3.44) are often manifested; while technology destruction (3.36) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.56 denotes the extent to which learning action cell sessions are often manifested; thus, they are extensive. Delos Reyes and Torio (2021) shared that the concept of rapport and learner autonomy in the field of education is often untouched in varied contexts, including the CVIF-DLP, which shows a systems approach to process-induced learning specifically designed to train learners to learn autonomously or independently. In this approach, learners are only provided interven-

tion whenever the need arises, allowing them to learn with little to no assistance of the teacher; thus, the development of rapport between teachers and learners might diminish, compared to a conventional teaching approach that is teacher-centered, where more rapport may be provided due to more interaction between teacher and learner. The results revealed an overall moderate, positive, and very significant correlation across all groups. Therefore, rejecting the generalization that most learners in their adolescence have lower rapport with their teachers as they mature; moreover, autonomy-supportive attitudes might have been a foundation instilled among learners by their teachers in the approach. The conclusion led to mediating factors such as the teaching approach itself and a strong guidance program.

Rapport-building is perceived to enhance engagement, level of gratification, and collaboration, resulting in better student engagement in the learning process. Almusharraf, (2022) measures the extent to which postsecondary instructors promote a meaningful online environment

through faculty-student rapport (FSR) in undergraduate English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms. This study is grounded on social constructivism and self-determination theoretical frameworks, suggesting that building meaningful environments aids students' investment

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport

No	Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	diverse learning styles	3.44	Extensive
2	technology distractions	3.36	Moderately Extensive
3	special needs students	3.89	Extensive
4	transitions and mobility	3.46	Extensive
5	teacher burn out	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.56	Extensive

and engagement in learning. The study utilizes a questionnaire and classroom observations to explore the relationship between FSR and students' level of engagement. The results revealed a significant difference between the rapport-building and nonrapport-building groups at a personal and academic level. The findings shed light on student attitudes about various instructional practices and techniques that play a critical role in building a safe, proactive, dynamic, and engaging online environment. Further research is required to reduce the issues related to physical distancing, emotional expressions, and technological competence. Technical competency is the primary prerequisite of any specialized activity; consequently, instructors need to assess learners' knowledge and accessibility within the learning community. Reflective practice is recommended for faculty members who are thus encouraged to continuously reflect

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of reading engagement. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: interactions in reading material (3.86), use of reading strategy (3.54), and sustained focus (3.44) are often manifested; independent reading choices (3.16) is sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.50 denotes the extent of reading engage-

on their teaching practice, redirect and modify their performance to meet their learners' specific needs, and design and maintain a healthy and encouraging relationship with individual students. Irwin (2022) describes using screen-cast feedback to enhance teaching presence and weekly self-reflection surveys to enhance social presence among students and build a community of learners. These approaches were found to diminish the feeling of isolation in online learning environments. Further findings indicated that this multimodal approach to providing feedback helped build a rapport between the teacher and students, which led to increased motivation and task engagement. These strategies to build a community of learners will particularly interest educators looking for innovative approaches to improving teaching and social presence in online learning environments while providing personalized, formative feedback.

ment, which is oftentimes manifested and thus extensive. Reading comprehension is critical for almost every aspect of life. Using PISA 2018 Turkey data, this study aims to reveal the relations among students' perceptions of their Turkish language teachers' behaviors that encourage reading engagement, levels of reading enjoyment, reading self-efficacy, and reading success within the frame of a model.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Reading Engagement

No	Reading Engagement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	interaction in reading material	3.86	Extensive
2	use of reading strategy	3.54	Extensive
3	sustained focus	3.44	Extensive
4	independent reading choices	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.50	Extensive

According to the research findings, teachers' behaviors that encourage students' reading engagement (TBESRE), reading enjoyment, and reading self-efficacy significantly affect reading achievement. In addition, TBESRE has significant indirect effects on reading achievement through reading enjoyment and self-efficacy. Reading self-efficacy has a significant indirect effect on reading achievement through reading enjoyment. Considering the findings of this study, it is recommended that teachers implement practices to encourage students' participation in reading activities and develop educational interventions to improve reading enjoyment and reading self-efficacy (Urfali Dadandi, 2022). This study examined the relations of early literacy activities and skills to reading dispositions, reading engagement, and reading achievement among fourth-grade students in the United Arab Emirates who took part in the English and Arabic versions of the 2016 Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS). The study also investigated the mediational roles of reading dispositions and reading engagement in the association between early literacy activities and skills and reading achievement among these fourth-grade students in the United Arab Emirates. Results of multigroup path analyses, after accounting

for student and family demographic characteristics, suggested that early literacy activities and skills were significantly positively associated with reading dispositions, reading engagement, and reading achievement in English and Arabic among fourth-grade students in the United Arab Emirates who took the PIRLS 2016 reading assessments in English and Arabic. Moreover, one of the reading dispositions, confidence in reading, mediated the associations between early literacy activities and skills and reading achievement in English and Arabic among fourth-grade students in the United Arab Emirates. Implications of the findings for policy and practice are discussed (Al et al., 2019).

Significant Relationship between Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport and Reading Engagement

Table 3 revealed the significant relationship between challenges of teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis must be rejected, stating that there is no significant relationship, for it provided empirical evidence to show its correlation. It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant strong and positive correlation between challenges of teacher-learner rapport ($r=0.897$; $p<.000$) and reading engagement.

The challenges associated with establishing and maintaining a solid teacher-learner rapport can significantly impact reading engagement among students. A positive and support-

ive teacher-student relationship is fundamental for creating a conducive learning environment, especially in literacy and reading-focused activities. When communication barriers, cultural

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport and Reading Engagement

Variables	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation	Decision
Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport				
Reading Engagement	0.897	<0.000	Significant	Reject H_0

differences, or a lack of understanding of individual student needs arise, the rapport between the teacher and learners may be strained. This can reduce students’ motivation and interest in reading (Al et al., 2019). A teacher’s ability to connect with learners personally is crucial for fostering a love for reading, as it creates a sense of trust and security. Challenges in rapport can result in students feeling disengaged, less likely to participate in reading-related discussions, and hesitant to seek guidance or clarification. Additionally, a strained teacher-learner relationship may hinder the development of a supportive classroom culture, where students feel encouraged to express their thoughts and opinions about the reading material (Urfali Dadandi, 2022).. To address these challenges, teachers must actively work on building rapport through effective communication, cultural sensitivity, and understanding of diverse learning needs. By overcoming these challenges, educators can create a positive and inclusive learning environment that promotes reading engagement and contributes to the overall academic success of their students (Wielers et al., 2022).

Domains of Challenges of Teacher-Learner

A

robust teacher-learner relationship fosters a supportive learning environment, particularly in literacy. If challenges persist, students may become disengaged, reluctant to actively participate in reading discussions, and less likely to seek assistance or clarification. Furthermore, a faltering rapport can impede the development of

Rapport Significantly Influence Reading Engagement

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on challenges of teacher-learner rapport that significantly influence reading engagement. Domains of challenges of teacher-learner rapport in terms of diverse learning styles (0.001), technology destructions (0.010), special needs students (0.002), transitions and mobility (0.000), and teacher burnout (0.000) significantly influenced reading engagement. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.879 suggests that 87.9% of the variance in reading engagement is explained by the challenges of teacher-learner rapport. Gregersen et al. (2021) shared that the connection between teachers and learners can be strained when rapport encounters difficulties, such as communication breakdowns, cultural disparities, or a lack of understanding of individual learning styles. This strain can manifest in decreased enthusiasm and interest in reading activities. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (254.588) and F-statistic are significant $p < 0.010$, which indicates that the model better predicts reading engagement.

a collaborative classroom atmosphere where students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and engaging with the material (Wielers et al., 2022). Fairman et al. (2023) said that to mitigate these challenges, educators must address communication gaps, be culturally sensitive, and tailor their approach to accommodate di-

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Challenges of Teacher-Learner Rapport Significantly Influencing Reading Engagement

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions
<i>H₀</i>					
(Intercept)	4.145		0.079	60.416	0.001
<i>H₁</i>					
(Intercept)	0.313		0.175	1.066	0.270
Diverse Learning Style	0.807	0.102	0.107	1.010	0.315
Technology Destructions	0.441	0.136	0.108	1.299	0.196
Special Needs students	0.202	0.210	0.097	2.098	0.038
Transition and Mobility	0.921	0.136	0.508	1.299	0.296
Teacher Burn-out	0.502	0.210	0.057	3.098	0.038

verse learning preferences. Overcoming these challenges strengthens the teacher-learner bond and contributes to a more positive and inclu-

sive learning environment, ultimately enhancing reading engagement and the overall educational experience for students.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion, and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study’s findings, which are given in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of teacher-learner rapport in terms of special needs students, teacher burnout, transitions and mobility, and diverse learning styles is often manifested, while technology destructions are sometimes manifested, thus extensive. The extent of reading engagement in terms of interactions with reading material, use of reading strategy, and sustained focus are often mani-

festes; independent reading choices are sometimes manifested, thus, extensive. Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement. Domains of teacher-learner rapport in terms of diverse learning styles, technology destructions, special needs students, transitions and mobility, and teacher burnout (significantly influenced reading engagement.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the con-

clusions, to wit; The extent of challenges of teacher-learner rapport in terms of special needs students, teacher burn-out, transitions and mobility, and diverse learning styles are often manifested, while technology destructions are sometimes manifested, thus extensive. The extent of reading engagement in terms of interactions with reading material, use of reading strategy, and sustained focus is often manifested; independent reading choices are sometimes manifested; thus, it is extensive. There is a significant relationship between challenges of teacher-learner rapport and reading engagement.

Domains of challenges to teacher-learner rapport, such as diverse learning styles, technology destruction, special needs students, transitions and mobility, and teacher burnout, significantly influenced reading engagement. The theory of teacher-learner rapport by Pasha-Zaidi (2022), centers on the fundamental idea that the relationship quality between educators and students profoundly impacts the teaching and learning process. This theory underscores the significance of fostering a positive and supportive connection between teachers and learners as a foundational element of effective education. It emphasizes that when teachers establish trust, respect, and open communication with students, it paves the way for more meaningful interactions in the classroom. The theory recognizes that rapport-building is not limited to the exchange of knowledge but also encompasses the emotional and social dimensions of learning. A strong teacher-learner rapport can inspire motivation, engagement, and a sense of belonging among students, ultimately enhancing their academic performance and overall well-being. Meanwhile, theory of reading engagement (Arya, 2020) posits that individuals' active involvement and emotional connection with reading materials are pivotal in fostering a lifelong love for reading and enhancing literacy skills. This theory underscores that reading goes beyond the mechanical decoding of words;

it is a dynamic process influenced by personal motivation, interests, and the context in which reading occurs. It emphasizes that deeply engaged readers are more likely to comprehend, retain, and critically analyze the content they encounter. This theory recognizes that various factors, including intrinsic motivation, text relevance, accessibility to reading materials, and a supportive reading environment, influence reading engagement. It also acknowledges that reading engagement is not a one-size-fits-all concept and may manifest differently in individuals based on their age, interests, and experiences.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. The supervisor may prioritize ongoing professional development programs that address the nuances of building strong teacher-learner rapport, emphasizing effective communication strategies and cultural sensitivity. Additionally, the supervisor can advocate for incorporating relationship-building components in teacher evaluation criteria, recognizing rapport's crucial role in fostering reading engagement. School Principal. May play a vital role in creating a positive school culture. They should encourage an environment that values and supports meaningful connections between teachers and students. Principals can facilitate regular teacher opportunities to share experiences and best rapport-building practices. Furthermore, principals should consider incorporating teacher-learner relationship dynamics into professional development plans and staff meetings. Teacher: Teachers may actively engage in professional development opportunities focused on improving teacher-learner rapport. They can benefit from training that enhances their communication skills, cultural competence, and understanding of diverse learning styles. Incorporating relationship-building activities into classroom routines and being attentive to individual student needs can contribute to a more support-

ive and engaging learning environment. Future strategies to overcome these challenges, considering cultural, socio-economic, and educational context variables. Additionally, longitudinal studies could provide insights into the long-term effects of positive teacher-learner rapport on reading outcomes.

Researcher. May delve deeper into the challenges teachers encounter in building rapport with diverse student populations and the subsequent impact on reading engagement. Research efforts could explore effective interventions and

5. References

- AITF For the Management of Infectious Diseases
<https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/downloads/2021/05may/20210520-IATF->
- Al Jefri, Hanan Mohamed; Aarepattamanni, Shaljan (2019). Examining the Relations of Early Literacy Activities and Skills to Reading Dispositions, Engagement, and Achievement among Fourth-Grade Students in the United Arab Emirates *Social Psychology of Education: An International Journal*, v22 n4 p901-920 Sep 2019 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11218-019-09504-7>
- Al Shlowiy, Ahmed (2022). Teacher's Reflection on Students' Engagement in Online Language Learning: Multi-Case Study *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, v8 n2 p285-295 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Teacher-Learner+Rapport+on+Reading+engagement&id=EJ1345103>
- Almasri, Firas (2022). Simulations to Teach Science Subjects: Connections among Students' Engagement, Self-Confidence, Satisfaction, and Learning Styles *Education and Information Technologies*, v27 n5 p7161-7181 Jun 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10940-w>
- Almusharraf, Norah (2022). Coconstructing a Meaningful Online Environment: Faculty-Student Rapport in the English as a Foreign Language College Classroom *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, v41 n2 p70-81 Sum 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/emip.12471>
- Altalhab, Sultan (2019). The Use of Reading Strategies amongst Saudi University EFL Students *Journal of Education and Learning*, v8 n3 p234-241 2019 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=the+use+of+reading+strategies+&id=EJ1217097>
- Anyichie, Aloysius C.; Butler, Deborah L.; Perry, Nancy E.; Nashon, Samson M. (2023). Examining Classroom Contexts in Support of Culturally Diverse Learners' Engagement: An Integration of Self-Regulated Learning and Culturally Responsive Pedagogical Practices *Frontline Learning Research*, v11 n1 p1-39 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=diverse+learning+styles+in+reading+engagement+&id=EJ1388551>
- Arya, Diana; Clairmont, Anthony; Katz, Daniel; Maul, Andrew (2020). Measuring Reading Strategy Use *Educational Assessment*, v25 n1 p5-30 2020 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10627197.2019.1702464>

- Bonner, Euan; Garvey, Kevin; Miner, Matthew; Godin, Sam; Reinders, Hayo (2023). Measuring Real-Time Learner Engagement in the Japanese EFL Classroom *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, v17 n2 p254-264 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2021.2025379>
- Creighton, Maria Victoria (2020). Relationship of Reader Engagement, Time Spent Reading Independently with Reader Comprehension *ProQuest LLC*, Ed.D. Dissertation, Brenau University <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=sustained+focused+in+reading+engagement&id=ED624977>
- Dao, Phung; Nguyen, Mai Xuan Nhat Chi; Iwashita, Noriko (2021). Teachers' Perceptions of Learner Engagement in L2 Classroom Task-Based Interaction *Language Learning Journal*, v49 n6 p711-724 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2019.1666908>
- Delos Reyes, Ryan Dave G.; Torio, Von Anthony G. (2021). The Relationship of Expert Teacher-Learner Rapport and Learner Autonomy in the CVIF-Dynamic Learning Program *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, v30 n5 p471-481 Oct 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40299-020-00532-y>
- Dickerson, Katie (2015). Reimagining Reading: Creating a Classroom Culture That Embraces Independent Choice Reading *Penn GSE Perspectives on Urban Education*, v12 n1 Spr 2015 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=independent+reading+choices&id=EJ1056721>
- Ditzler, Christine; Hong, Eunsook; Strudler, Neal (2016). How Tablets Are Utilized in the Classroom *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, v48 n3 p181-193 2016 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2016.1172444>
- Dockett, Sue; Perry, Bob (2021). Invisible Transitions: Transitions to School Following Different Paths *Australasian Journal of Early Childhood*, v46 n3 p224-235 Sep 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/18369391211009698>
- Fairman, Janet C.; Smith, David J.; Pullen, Paige C.; Lebel, Steve J. (2023). The Challenge of Keeping Teacher Professional Development Relevant *Professional Development in Education*, v49 n2 p197-209 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2020.1827010>
- Flack, Caleb E.; Garbacz, S. Andrew; Stormshak, Elizabeth A.; McIntyre, Laura Lee (2021). A Longitudinal Study of Home-Based Involvement and Dyadic Adjustment during the Transition to Early Elementary School *School Psychology*, v38 n5 p287-293 Sep 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/spq0000543>

- Gregersen, Tammy; Mercer, Sarah; MacIntyre, Peter D. (2021). Language Teacher Perspectives on Stress and Coping *Foreign Language Annals*, v54 n4 p1145-1163 Win 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/flan.12544>
- Harding, Lauren Howard (2023). Supporting Diverse Learning Styles: A Case Study in Student Led Syllabus Design *Journal of Political Science Education*, v19 n1 p83-90 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15512169.2022.2117626>
- Heck, Ronald H.; Reid, Tingting; Leckie, George (2022). Incorporating Student Mobility in Studying Academic Growth in Math: Comparing Several Alternative Multilevel Formulations *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, v33 n4 p516-543 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2022.2060265>
- Herrera, Socorro G.; Rodriguez, Diane; Cabral, Robin M.; Holmes, Melissa A. (2023) Equitable and Inclusive Teaching for Diverse Learners with Disabilities: A Biography-Driven Approach *Teachers College Press* <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=special+needs+learner+challenges+reading+engagement&id=ED628755>
- Indriani, Siane; Suteja, Hanna (2023). Fostering Reading Interest through Digital Storytelling for Young Learners in the Early Childhood *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, v17 n2 p301-306 May 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=interest+in+reading+materials+among+young+learners&id=EJ1386142>
- Irwin, Bradley (2022). Strategies to Build a Community of Learners in Online Classes *Research-publishing.net*, Paper presented at the EUROCALL 2022 Conference (30th, Reykjavik, Iceland, Aug 17-19, 2022) <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Teacher-Learner+Rapport+on+Reading+engagement&id=ED625192>
- Javed, Misbah; Lashari, Tahira Anwar; Khan, Safdar Abbas; Lashari, Sana Anwar; Khan, Amna; Afzal, Erum; Maqbool, Maajid (2023). *International Journal of Whole Schooling*, v19 n1 p96-116 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=diverse+learning+styles+in+reading+engagement+&pg=2&id=EJ1384566>
- Kearney, Sean; Maakrun, Julie (2020). Let's Get Engaged: The Nexus between Digital Technologies, Engagement and Learning *Education Sciences*, v10 Article 357 2020 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=technology+distractions+&id=EJ1279844>
- Lazarus, Kelechi Uchemadu (2021). Classroom Environmental Factors as Correlates of Reading Engagement among Secondary School Students with Learning Disabilities in Ibadan, Nigeria *Journal of the International Association of Special Education*, v21 n1 p11-21 2021 <https://iase.org/journal>

- Lee, Yongjun; Jang, Bong Gee; Conradi Smith, Kristin (2021). A Systematic Review of Reading Engagement Research: What Do We Mean, What Do We Know, and Where Do We Need to Go? *Reading Psychology*, v42 n5 p540-576 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2021.1888359>
- Mulling, Alessandra Belletti Figueira; Watkins, Peter (2022). Reading in Self-Access Material: What Can We Learn from Self-Instructed Learners and Their Reported Experience? *Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, v22 n1 p37-55 Apr 2022 <http://www.readingmatrix.com/files/27-ajpntanm.pdf>
- Namaziandost, Ehsan; Razmi, Mohammad Hasan; Ahmad Tilwani, Shouket; Pourhosein Gilakjani, Abbas (2022). The Impact of Authentic Materials on Reading Comprehension, Motivation, and Anxiety among Iranian Male EFL Learners *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, v38 n1 p1-18 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10573569.2021.1892001>
- Neuwirth, Lorenz S. (2022). Flipd App Reduces Cellular Phone Distractions in the Traditional College Classroom: Implications for Enriched Discussions and Student Retention *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, v24 n2 p386-420 Aug 2022
- Pasha-Zaidi, Nausheen; Hines, Valneshia; Afari, Ernest (2022). More than Words: A Study of Ethnic Identity, Reading Self-Efficacy, and Reading Practices of Hispanic American and African American Adults *Reading Psychology*, v43 n2 p105-128 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2021.1888343>
- Par, Leonardus (2020). The Relationship between Reading Strategies and Reading Achievement of the EFL Students *International Journal of Instruction*, v13 n2 p223-238 Apr 2020 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=the+use+of+reading+strategies+&id=EJ1249084>
- Phillips, Heather N. (2023). Developing Critical Thinking in Classrooms: Teacher Responses to a Reading-for-Meaning Workshop *Reading & Writing: Journal of the Reading Association of South Africa*, v14 n1 Article 401 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Teacher+Learner+Rapport+on+Reading+engagement&id=EJ1382960>
- Urfali Dadandi, Pakize; Dadandi, Ibrahim (2022). The Relationships among Teachers' Behaviours That Encourage Students' Reading Engagement, Reading Enjoyment, Reading Self-Efficacy and Reading Success *Participatory Educational Research*, v9 n3 p98-110 May 2022 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=reading+engagement+among+early+schoolers&id=EJ1324871>

- Roberts, Sarana Eyire; Lee, Yeunjoo (2023). Strategies and Challenges to Teaching Students with Special Needs during a Pandemic *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, p112-130 Win 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=special+needs+learner+challenges+reading+engagement&id=EJ1371976>
- Rouse, Elizabeth; Nicholas, Maria; Garner, Rosemarie (2023). School Readiness -- What Does This Mean? Educators' Perceptions Using a Cross Sector Comparison *International Journal of Early Years Education*, v31 n1 p185-199 2023 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09669760.2020.1733938>
- Sande, Lisa van der; Wildeman, Ilona; Bus, Adriana G.; van Steensel, Roel (2022). Personalized Expert Guidance of Students' Book Choices in Primary and Secondary Education *Reading Psychology*, v43 n5-6 p380-404 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2022.2113944>
- Schwartz, Lisa A.; Geier, Michael T.; Stowe, Kristin (2021). Understanding Distractors in a Business Technology Classroom *Journal of Instructional Pedagogies*, v25 Jan 2021 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=technology+distractions+&id=EJ1294593>
- Selwyn, Neil; Aagaard, Jesper (2021). Banning Mobile Phones from Classrooms--An Opportunity to Advance Understandings of Technology Addiction, Distraction and Cyberbullying *British Journal of Educational Technology*, v52 n1 p8-19 Jan 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12943>
- Sefotho, Maximus Monaheng; Onyishi, Charity N. (2021). In-School Transition Challenges among Primary School Learners with Autism Spectrum Disorders in South Africa: Parents and Teachers' Perspectives *Perspectives in Education*, v39 n2 p283-302 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.18820/2519593X/pie.v39.i2.20>
- Simmons, Ben (2021). The Production of Social Spaces for Children with Profound and Multiple Learning Difficulties: A Lefebvrian Analysis *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, v42 n5-6 p828-844 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2021.1922269>
- van der Sande, Lisa; van Steensel, Roel; Fikrat-Wevers, Suzanne; Arends, Lidia (2023). Effectiveness of Interventions That Foster Reading Motivation: A Meta-Analysis *Educational Psychology Review*, v35 n1 Article 21 Mar 2023

- Višnjic Jevtic, Adrijana; Halavuk, Antonija (2021). Early Childhood Teachers and Burn-Out Syndrome -- Perception of Croatian Teachers *Early Years: An International Journal of Research and Development*, v41 n1 p36-47 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09575146.2018.1482260>
- Wielers, Rudi; Hummel, Lisa; van der Meer, Peter (2022). Career Insecurity and Burnout Complaints of Young Dutch Workers *Journal of Education and Work*, v35 n2 p227-240 2022 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13639080.2021.2018412>
- Williams, Kelly J.; Martinez, Leticia R.; Fall, Anna-Maria; Miciak, Jeremy; Vaughn, Sharon (2023). Student Engagement among High School English Learners with Reading Comprehension Difficulties *Grantees Submission, School Psychology Review* v52 n1 p38-56 2023 <https://doi.org/10.1080/2372966X.2020.1868948>
- Wozniak, Cheryl L. (2011). Reading and Talking about Books: A Critical Foundation for Intervention *Voices from the Middle*, v19 n2 p17-21 Dec 2011 <http://www.ncte.org/journals/vm/issues/v19-2>
- Xu, Ying; Yau, Joanna C.; Reich, Stephanie M. (2021). Press, Swipe and Read: Do Interactive Features Facilitate Engagement and Learning with e-Books? *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, v37 n1 p212-225 Feb 2021 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12480>
- Yangin Ersanli, Ceylan (2023). The Effect of Using Augmented Reality with Storytelling on Young Learners' Vocabulary Learning and Retention *Novitas-ROYAL (Research on Youth and Language)*, v17 n1 p62-72 2023 <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=interest+in+reading+materials+among+young+learners&id=EJ1389077>